

Modeling the Impact of Climate Change on Irrigation Water Requirements of Watermelon Using CROPWAT 8.0

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Abstract

For water resources to be sustainable, it is very important to predict the impacts of climate change very well and develop strategies for adaptation. This study aims to model the impact of possible climate change on plant water consumption (ET_c) and irrigation water requirements (IWR) in watermelon cultivation. To achieve this goal, 36 scenarios were created considering the increase and decrease of minimum and maximum temperatures (1, 2, 3 °C) and precipitation (10%, 20%, 30%) in the climate data of the reference period 1940-2024 in watermelon cultivation in Tekirdağ and the effects of possible climate change on ET_c and IWR were modeled in line with these scenarios. As a result, it was determined that ET_c values will vary between 376.9-447.2 mm season⁻¹, and IWR values will vary between 246.0-367.8 mm season⁻¹. When temperatures increase by 1, 2, and 3 °C compared to the reference period, ET_c values increase by 2.8%, 5.7% and 8.6%, respectively, while when temperatures decrease by 1, 2, and 3 °C, ET_c values decrease by 2.9%, 5.7% and 8.5%, respectively. IWR values range from -18.5% to 21.9% compared to the reference period. While ET_c varies in direct proportion with temperature change, IWR varies in inverse proportion with precipitation change. It is thought that this study will guide managers, practitioners, and decision makers.

Research Article

Article History

Received :10.06.2025
Accepted :15.07.2025

Keywords

Citrullus lanatus
crop water requirement
water resources management

1. Introduction

The IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) report and a number of national and international scientific model studies have suggested that Türkiye will have a warmer, drier climate in the near future. When climate change is evaluated in terms of precipitation, studies have revealed that Türkiye will have a more uncertain climate structure (Anonymous, 2025a). Climate change assessments made with various models and scenarios in the TR21 Thrace Region, where Tekirdağ is located, have also predicted increases in temperature and variability in precipitation (Hanedar et al., 2019; Deveci and Konukcu, 2016). Changing patterns in the water cycle due to climate change will cause significant changes in the quality and supply of water resources and affect many climate-dependent sectors, including food production, where water is vital. Türkiye is now a country trying to adapt its agricultural activities to

current climatic conditions (Anonymous, 2025a).

When watermelon production in the world is evaluated in 2022, Türkiye (3.400.000 tons) ranks second after China (60.400.000 tons) (Anonymous, 2025b). According to 2024 TurkStat statistics, 3.198.000 tons of watermelon were produced in Türkiye (Anonymous, 2025c). This shows that watermelon production in Türkiye is decreasing. In Tekirdağ, watermelon is a vegetable known for its thin rind and few seeds, for which festivals are organized (Anonymous, 2025d). The change in watermelon cultivation areas and production amount in Tekirdağ is shown in Table 1. When the change in the last five years is analyzed, the cultivation areas and production amount decreased in the 2023-2024 period compared to the 2020-2022 period. Therefore, it is a vegetable whose production should be supported.

Table 1. Change in watermelon cultivation areas and production amounts over the years in Tekirdağ (Anonymous, 2025c)

Years	Planted area (ha)	Production amount (ton)
2020	951	42.292
2021	975	45.311
2022	1039	57.225
2023	724	30.938
2024	822	32.023

The CROPWAT model is a reliable tool that helps predict how agricultural water needs might change and supports decision-making for managing water resources (Golfam et al., 2025). In the world, studies have been conducted with CROPWAT to determine the impact of climate change on irrigation water requirements of watermelon (Saraive et al., 2016; Enyew et al., 2020; Olotu, 2024). In Türkiye, there are many studies with CROPWAT in which different plant species are preferred. In Türkiye, there are many studies with CROPWAT in which different plant species are preferred. In Türkiye, studies on drought tolerance of watermelon (Daşgan et al., 2021), irrigation types and their effects on watermelon (Çamoğlu et al., 2010; Özmen et

al., 2014; Duraktekin et al., 2018) were found. In the Thrace Region, a study on watermelon was conducted by Polat et al. (2017), and it was observed that the studies were quite limited. This study is one of the first in Türkiye to apply the CROPWAT 8.0 model specifically to watermelon cultivation under climate change conditions. This study presents a simulation-based approach that contributes to the broader field of climate-smart agriculture by utilizing the CROPWAT 8.0 model under various climate scenarios. Today, various climate scenarios are used to determine the effects of climate change. Each scenario makes inferences about the future within different ranges and with optimistic and pessimistic approaches (Baydar et al., 2025). In this

context, this study aims to contribute to literature by utilizing a wide range of scenarios created with increases and decreases in temperature and precipitation. The study aimed to model the effect of climate change on the irrigation water requirements (IWR) of watermelon using CROPWAT 8.0. To achieve this objective, climate scenarios were created considering the increase and decrease of minimum and maximum temperatures (1, 2, 3 °C) and precipitation (10%, 20%, 30%) in the climate data for the reference period 1940-2024 and the changes of plant water consumption (ET_c) and IWR were examined and evaluated in line with these scenarios. Thus, it is thought that this study will guide managers, practitioners, and decision makers in the process of adaptation to climate change

by trying to determine how the irrigation water requirements of watermelon will change in a possible climate change.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Research area

Tekirdağ is one of the three provinces located in the northwest of Türkiye, north of the Marmara Sea, entirely in the territory of Thrace. Tekirdağ lies between $41^{\circ} 34' 52'' - 40^{\circ} 52' 53'' - 41^{\circ} 35' 28'' - 40^{\circ} 32' 23''$ N latitude and $28^{\circ} 09' 14'' - 26^{\circ} 42' 42'' - 28^{\circ} 08' 34'' - 26^{\circ} 54' 24''$ E longitude. The province has a surface area of 6.313 km² and its altitude is between 0-200 m above sea level (Anonymous, 2025e). The location of the research area is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research area

2.2. Climate of the research area

Long-term climate data of Tekirdağ are shown in Table 2. Accordingly, the total precipitation for many years is 577.5 mm, and the average temperature is 14.1 °C (Anonymous, 2025f). According to the general humidity indices, Tekirdağ falls within the semi-humid climate type among the hydrographic regions. In terms of precipitation regime, it is in the Mediterranean precipitation

regime category. In the coastal strip of Tekirdağ, where the effects of the Mediterranean climate are observed, summers are hot, and winters are mild. In the coastal strip, which includes the Ergene basin, the land climate is rather dominant. The type of precipitation falling on the land is usually rain, and snowfall is rare. On average, the least precipitation is observed in August and the most precipitation in December in Tekirdağ (Anonymous, 2025g).

Table 2. Long-term (1940-2024) climate data for Tekirdağ (Anonymous, 2025f)

Months	Avg. Min. Temperature (°C)	Avg. Max. Temperature (°C)	Avg. Mean Temperature (°C)	Relative Humidity (%)	Wind Speed (m s ⁻¹)	Avg. Daily Sunshine (hour)	Precipitation (mm)
January	2.1	8.1	4.9	82.3	3.1	2.7	67.9
February	2.5	9.1	5.5	80.5	3.0	3.5	54.2
March	4.2	11.1	7.3	79.5	2.9	4.4	53.5
April	8.2	15.8	11.8	76.9	2.4	6.0	42.3
May	12.7	20.6	16.7	76.3	2.2	7.5	37.1
June	16.8	25.4	21.2	72.4	2.4	8.6	37.8
July	19.1	28.1	23.8	68.6	2.7	9.5	23.5
August	19.5	28.3	23.9	69.2	2.9	8.6	15.3
September	16.2	24.5	20.3	72.8	2.8	6.9	32.7
October	12.1	19.6	15.7	78.1	2.8	5.0	59.5
November	8.2	14.8	11.3	81.7	2.7	3.2	73.8
December	4.4	10.5	7.3	82.5	3.0	2.5	79.9
Avg./Total	10.5	18.0	14.1	76.7	2.7	5.7	577.5

2.3. Climate data

The climate data used in this study were obtained from the Tekirdağ Meteorological Station Directorate. These data include long-term minimum temperature (°C), maximum temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind speed (m s⁻¹), sunshine duration (hours), and precipitation (mm) for the period 1940-2024. These data were used monthly in CROPWAT 8.0.

2.4. Plant data

The plant data related to watermelon used in the study were obtained from the “Plant Water Consumption Guide for Irrigated Crops in Türkiye” and shown in Table 3. These data are planting date, crop development period (initial, development, mid-season, late-season), and K_c values (K_{c1}, K_{c3}, K_{c4}).

Table 3. Plant parameters for watermelon (Anonymous, 2017)

Plant	Planting Date	Crop Development Period (days)				Total (days)	K _c Values		
		Initial	Development	Mid-Season	Late-Season		K _{c1}	K _{c3}	K _{c4}
Watermelon	April 25th	30	22	41	29	123	0.36	0.97	0.73

Table 4. Properties of the medium soil class (Anonymous, 2024)

Parameters	Values
Maximum rooting depth (cm)	900
Total available soil moisture (mm m ⁻¹)	290
Initial available soil moisture (mm m ⁻¹)	290
Initial soil moisture depletion (%)	0
Maximum rain infiltration rate (mm day ⁻¹)	40

2.5. Soil data

The study used data from the FAO-defined medium soil class in CROPWAT 8.0. The properties of this soil class are shown in Table 4.

2.6. CROPWAT 8.0

CROPWAT 8.0 is a decision support tool developed by FAO (Food and Agriculture

Organization) (Anonymous, 2024). Inputs to CROPWAT are meteorological parameters (temperature, precipitation, wind speed, sunshine hours, and relative humidity), crop parameters (planting and harvest date, crop coefficient, root length, and crop factor), and soil parameters (soil texture, available soil water, infiltration rate, and soil water content at planting date). As output, CROPWAT

provides the results of reference plant water consumption, plant water consumption, irrigation water requirement of the plant, irrigation system development, evaluation of the effect of rain or insufficient irrigation on yield, and daily water budget analysis (Kartal et al., 2019). In making these calculations, CROPWAT relies on two FAO publications of the Irrigation and Drainage Series (No. 56: Crop Evapotranspiration-Guidelines for computing crop water requirements and No. 33 Yield response to water) (Doorenbos and Kassam, 1979; Allen et al., 1998).

2.7. Methods

The method followed in the study is shown in Figure 2. Within the scope of the research, firstly, climate data covering the long period 1940-2024 were obtained from the Tekirdağ Meteorological Station Directorate. These data are monthly average values from directly

measured station data for the period 1940-2024. No gap-filling or correction methods were applied to these data within the scope of the study. 36 scenarios were created using monthly climate data, in which minimum and maximum temperatures (1, 2, 3 °C) and precipitation (10%, 20%, 30%) increase and decrease. When naming these scenarios, temperature is represented by T and precipitation by P. For example, the T (-1), P (+10%) scenario is the scenario in which the minimum and maximum temperatures decrease by 1°C and precipitation increases by 10%. The ET_c and IWR values were calculated by running the model with the climate data organized according to these scenarios, the plant data obtained for watermelon, and the medium soil data in CROPWAT 8.0. These calculated values were compared and evaluated with the long-term results of 1940-2024, which are considered a reference.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the method followed in the study

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the study are summarized in Table 5. Compared to the reference period, when temperatures increased by 1, 2, and 3 °C, ET_c values increased by 2.8%, 5.7% and 8.6% respectively, while temperatures decreased by 1, 2, and 3 °C, ET_c values decreased by 2.9%, 5.7% and 8.5% respectively. The highest ET_c value was 447.2 mm season⁻¹ in scenarios

where the temperature increased by 3 °C, while the lowest ET_c value was 376.9 mm season⁻¹ in scenarios where the temperature decreased by 3 °C. Figure 3 also clearly shows that in the scenarios compared to the reference period (1940-2024), ET_c values increase when temperatures increase and ET_c values decrease when temperatures decrease. Deveci et al. (2025a) estimated ET_c and IWR for canola and

wheat in the future years based on HadGEM2-ES and MPI-ESM-MR models, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. As a result, they predicted that ET_c will increase with the increase in temperature in Tekirdağ, while precipitation will increase and decrease accordingly, since it varies from period to period. When these two studies were compared, it was observed that although the plants studied were different, the results showed a consistent trend with each other, depending on the climate factor.

When all scenarios in Table 5 are evaluated, it is determined that ET_c values will vary between 376.9-447.2 mm season⁻¹. Duraktekin et al. (2018) determined ET_c values as 379-486 mm season⁻¹ in Tarsus in 2017 under different irrigation conditions. In this study, the ET_c of the reference period was determined as 411.7 mm season⁻¹, and this value is within these limits. The ET_c value in this study is close to the lower end of the range determined for Adana (379 mm season⁻¹). Because Adana is a warmer region and is located further south, this is considered normal. Megna et al. (2013)

calculated ET_c and IWR for eleven major crops in India using the CROPWAT model at Kelappaji College of Agricultural Engineering and Technology and found ET_c for watermelon to be 427.4 mm season⁻¹. When these studies were compared in two different countries, the reason for such close values was attributed to the following. Although there were slight differences in many of the criteria compared, the most significant difference was attributed to the fact that the planting date (23.12.2011) and harvest date (11.14.2012) were quite different in India. In other words, due to climatic conditions, the growing time of the plant is quite different from the research area. This situation was also considered normal. ET_c is of great importance in the preparation of irrigation programs and irrigation projects (Taş and Kırnak, 2011). Therefore, it is important to be able to accurately determine ET_c and how it will be affected by climate change. This is because, at a time when water resources are so limited, it will enable irrigation planning to be carried out most economically and will lead to the efficient use of water.

Figure 3. ET_c values of watermelon in Tekirdağ

Table 5. ET_c and IWR values (mm season⁻¹) and deviations (%) from the reference period (1940-2024)

Reference Period and Scenarios	ET _c	IWR	Deviation from 1940-2024 (%)	
	(mm season ⁻¹)	(mm season ⁻¹)	ET _c	IWR
1940-2024	411.7	301.7	ET _c	IWR
T (+1), P (+10%)	423.3	303.2	2.8	0.5
T (+1), P (+20%)	423.3	296.3	2.8	-1.8
T (+1), P (+30%)	423.3	288.8	2.8	-4.3
T (+2), P (+10%)	435.2	315.2	5.7	4.5
T (+2), P (+20%)	435.2	307.2	5.7	1.8
T (+2), P (+30%)	435.2	299.7	5.7	-0.7
T (+3), P (+10%)	447.2	326.7	8.6	8.3
T (+3), P (+20%)	447.2	318.2	8.6	5.5
T (+3), P (+30%)	447.2	310.7	8.6	3.0
T (+1), P (-10%)	423.3	322.6	2.8	6.9
T (+1), P (-20%)	423.3	333.2	2.8	10.4
T (+1), P (-30%)	423.3	343.9	2.8	14.0
T (+2), P (-10%)	435.2	334.4	5.7	10.8
T (+2), P (-20%)	435.2	345.1	5.7	14.4
T (+2), P (-30%)	435.2	355.8	5.7	17.9
T (+3), P (-10%)	447.2	346.4	8.6	14.8
T (+3), P (-20%)	447.2	357.1	8.6	18.4
T (+3), P (-30%)	447.2	367.8	8.6	21.9
T (-1), P (+10%)	399.9	282.3	-2.9	-6.4
T (-1), P (+20%)	399.9	274.8	-2.9	-8.9
T (-1), P (+30%)	399.9	267.2	-2.9	-11.4
T (-2), P (+10%)	388.3	271.7	-5.7	-9.9
T (-2), P (+20%)	388.3	264.1	-5.7	-12.5
T (-2), P (+30%)	388.3	256.6	-5.7	-14.9
T (-3), P (+10%)	376.9	261.1	-8.5	-13.5
T (-3), P (+20%)	376.9	253.6	-8.5	-15.9
T (-3), P (+30%)	376.9	246.0	-8.5	-18.5
T (-1), P (-10%)	399.9	299.4	-2.9	-0.8
T (-1), P (-20%)	399.9	309.8	-2.9	2.7
T (-1), P (-30%)	399.9	320.5	-2.9	6.2
T (-2), P (-10%)	388.3	288.3	-5.7	-4.4
T (-2), P (-20%)	388.3	298.2	-5.7	-1.2
T (-2), P (-30%)	388.3	308.9	-5.7	2.4
T (-3), P (-10%)	376.9	277.4	-8.5	-8.1
T (-3), P (-20%)	376.9	286.8	-8.5	-4.9
T (-3), P (-30%)	376.9	297.4	-8.5	-1.4

Considering the IWR values, the highest IWR value (367.8 mm season⁻¹) was calculated in the scenario where the temperature increased by 3 °C and precipitation decreased the most (30%), while the lowest IWR (246.0 mm season⁻¹) was determined in the scenario where the temperature decreased the most and precipitation increased the most (30%). In addition, the IWR value for the reference period (1940-2024) was calculated as 301.7 mm season⁻¹. Compared to the reference period, IWR increased by 21.9% in the T (+3), P (-30%) scenario and decreased by 18.5% in

the T (-3), P (+30%) scenario. IWR values will vary between -18.5%-21.9% compared to the reference period. Diku et al. (2015) determined that IWR for watermelon will increase in future periods when temperatures increase and precipitation decreases in Albania. The results found in this study are in the same direction. When the results of 36 scenarios in which minimum and maximum temperatures (1, 2, 3 °C) and precipitation (10%, 20%, 30%) increase and decrease in the period 1940-2024 were evaluated, it was determined that IWR values will vary between 246.0-367.8 mm

season⁻¹. Figure 4 shows that IWR gradually decreased in scenarios where rainfall increased by 10%, 20% and 30%, while IWR gradually increased in scenarios where rainfall decreased (10%, 20% and 30%). Since irrigation is directly related to rainfall, it is considered likely that the results will be in this way. Enyew et al. (2020) stated that excessive water application can be detrimental to watermelon by causing plant diseases and decreasing fruit quality and yield. They also showed in their study that an appropriate irrigation regime significantly increases plant water use and yield. This shows the importance of determining the correct irrigation amount. Olotu (2024) found different values of crop water requirement for watermelon in Nigeria,

and Naik et al. (2015) found different values in two different regions of India. This can be explained as follows. Since climatic conditions, K_c values, planting time, vegetation period, period lengths, soil type, etc., vary from region to region, it is very difficult to achieve the same value. Especially, soil type change also affects IWR (Deveci et al., 2025b). Therefore, there are many factors that affect IWR. These factors vary from region to region and from plant to plant. In order to use water resources effectively and efficiently, it is of great importance to accurately predict climate change, which is a very complex process, and then develop strategies for adaptation and adjustment.

Figure 4. IWR values of watermelon in Tekirdağ

Research shows that watermelon will be affected by climate change (Paroon et al., 2019; Melo et al., 2020). Saraiva et al. (2016) estimated that IWR in Brazil (Teresina, PI) would increase by 5.9% for a 3.8 °C temperature increase (B2 scenario) and 11.9% for a 5.4 °C temperature increase (A2 scenario). Roushdi (2024) predicted that the CWR for watermelon in Egypt in 40 Global Circulation Models and two representative

concentration pathways (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) in both coastal and inland areas would increase every decade until 2100. Melo et al. (2020) evaluated the effects of temperature and relative humidity on ET_c and found that climate change caused a decrease in the vegetative cycle under A2 and B2 scenarios on two varieties in 2006 (February-April) and 2009 (September-November). Therefore, these studies show that watermelon is affected by

climate change in different ways. It is very important to accurately determine the effects of climate change on watermelon in the research area in order for watermelon to adapt to climate change and for decision makers to develop strategies.

There are some limitations to this study. One of these limitations is that calibration could not be performed because there were no field trials conducted simultaneously with this study. In addition, the soil type was accepted as medium soil class. The study examined only the effects of temperature and precipitation changes among climate parameters. Many factors affect IWR. Including other factors in the studies would provide a more comprehensive framework. K_c values, crop development period, and planting date are values specific to the Thrace Region and Tekirdağ and were taken from the guide titled "Plant Water Consumption Guide for Irrigated Crops in Türkiye" (Anonymous, 2017). This guide is a reliable database for Türkiye. This should be taken into consideration. In addition, this study has addressed a wide range of positive and negative temperature and precipitation change scenarios. By evaluating the responses of watermelon to IWR, the study has attempted to provide a comprehensive perspective on understanding the effects of climate change. It is thought that diversifying research by using climate data obtained from region-specific climate change prediction models would be beneficial.

4. Conclusion

In a period when water resources are very limited, it is of great importance to accurately predict possible climate change while planning water management. The impact of climate change on water management and agricultural irrigation is of great importance. In this study, the effects of possible climate change on ET_c and IWR were modeled with the scenarios created. As a result, these values vary according to the increases and decreases in temperature and precipitation. While ET_c varies directly proportional to temperature change, IWR varies inversely proportional to

precipitation change. Under these conditions, it would be a positive step to first predict possible climate change and then accurately determine ET_c and IWR when planning irrigation, leading to the use of water-saving irrigation methods such as drip irrigation. Thus, a positive contribution will be made to water resources. In addition, when planning water resources, determining the impact of climate change on the types of crops grown in each region and encouraging producers to use water resources efficiently will contribute positively to water resources.

Understanding how ET_c and IWR will be affected by climate change in watermelon cultivation will guide the adaptation process to climate change. To determine the effects of climate change on irrigation, it would be very useful to increase the number of studies by changing different parameters along with climate parameters such as temperature and precipitation, and by evaluating different plants, including criteria such as soil type change, planting harvest date change, etc., in the research.

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To Cite

Deveci, H., 2025. Modeling the Impact of Climate Change on Irrigation Water Requirements of Watermelon Using CROPWAT 8.0. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(3): 925-935. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16899680>.